

24TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
COMPOSITE MATERIALS (ICCM24)

UNIVERSITY OF DELAWARE
CENTER FOR
COMPOSITE MATERIALS
Celebrating 50 Years

Analysis of the image-based evaluation of the permeability of carbon-carbon composites

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Project Overview

Project Goal

- Improvement of the densification process of carbon-carbon composites.

Focus of Today's Presentation

- Identification of the minimum dimensions of the statistical representative volume element of carbon-carbon composites for permeability characterization.

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Outline

1. Introduction
 - I. Densification process of carbon-carbon composites
 - II. sRVE of carbon-carbon composites
2. Permeability of carbon-carbon composites as function of sample dimensions and inlet location
3. Image-based determination of the stochastic permeability
4. Numerical simulations for the prediction of the effective permeability
 - I. Sample of 5 plies
 - II. Sample of 33 plies
5. Conclusions

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Densification of Carbon-Carbon Composites

Manufacturing of Carbon/Carbon Composites

Matrix Degradation → Shrinkage and Weight Loss

Densification Process

- Repetition Infiltration/Pyrolysis.
- Takes several months to complete.

Densification process: Muhammed et al. 2021 *J. Mater. Sci.* DOI 10.1007/s10853-021-06401-3

Improvement of Densification of Carbon-Carbon Composites

How to improve the process?

- Tailor pyrolysis schedule to control porosity development.
- Find re-infiltration parameters to reduce infiltration time.

Characterization of permeability of carbon-carbon composites (CCC)

- Key parameter for characterization of connected porosity.
- Describes how gas generated during pyrolysis evacuate porosity.
- Determines how resin permeates connected pores during re-infiltration.
- Necessary for numerical simulations to improve the densification process.

Necessary to identify the minimum size of the statistical representative volume element (sRVE)

- Macro-cracks dimensions can be comparable or larger than fabric RVE (25 mm²).

Framework for the Identification of the sRVE

Permeability
Experiment

Sample of 5 plies

Measured Out-of-Plane
Permeability

Minimum Size
sRVE of CCC

Effective
Permeability

CT scan and
Digital Model

Sample of 5 plies

Red: composite blue: pores

Predicted 3D Permeability
Tensor and Permeability
Distribution

Numerical Simulations

Sample of 5 plies

Sample of 33 plies

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Permeability Experiments

Experiment Set-up

$$K = -\frac{2\mu_g L L_c}{P^2} \frac{\partial P}{\partial t}$$

Experiment Dimensions

Inlet Locations

Permeability of Carbon-Carbon Composites

- Experiments are computed with same method and measuring fluids.
- Microstructure of samples between experiments does not change: variation can be attributed only to local heterogeneity.

Measured Permeability

Sample size in-plane [mm ²]	Average ·10 ⁻¹⁴ [m ²]	Standard Deviation ·10 ⁻¹⁴ [m ²]
20 x 20	5.5	1.6
30 x 30	6.0	1.0
40 x 40	5.2	0.6
40 x 50	5.0	0.1

Coefficient of Variation (Cv)

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Image-Based Stokes and Stokes-Brinkman Solver PoroS

- Research software for the virtual characterization of porous materials developed at the Ecole Centrale de Nantes.
- **PoroS 1.0**: solves Stokes flows by finite element method (FEM) where the finite elements are the voxels (3D) or the pixels (2D) of CT images or digital twins.

Figure: P. Mulye et al. 2024 *Materials* DOI 10.3390/ma17122873

Image-Based Predicted Permeability of Carbon-Carbon Composites

- *PoroS* used to **predict the permeability tensors** of the 70 sub-domains.
- Permeability dependent on scale of experiment even for constant microstructure of CCC.

- Voxel size: 6 μm .
- Geometry divided in **70 sub-domains**.

Comparison of Experiment and Image-Based Permeability (z-dir)

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Numerical Simulations: Model Generation of Sample of 5 Plies

- Element dimensions equal to CT sub-domains dimensions.
- *Thickness* of sample of 5 plies equal to **1 sub-domain** in z-direction.
- Model in-plane dimensions increased from area of 3.5 mm^2 (1 element) to 35000 mm^2 (100 by 100 array of elements).

Numerical Simulations: Model Generation of Sample of 33 Plies

- Element dimensions equal to CT sub-domains dimensions.
- *Thickness* of sample of 33 plies equal to **6 sub-domains** in z-direction.
- Model in-plane dimensions increased from area of 3.5 mm² (1 element) to 35000 mm² (100 by 100 array of elements).

Numerical Simulations: Evaluation of the Effective Permeability

Sample of 5 plies

- Flow assumed parallel for effective permeability K_{eff} in out-of-plane direction.

$$K_{eff} = \frac{1}{A} \sum_i K_i A_i$$

K_i : permeability of i^{th} element.
 A_i : area of i^{th} element.
 A : area of numerical model.

Sample of 33 plies

- Effective permeability K_{eff} evaluated with software Liquid Injection Molding Simulations (LIMS).

$$K_{eff} = \frac{qL\mu}{A\Delta P}$$

q : flowrate.
 L : thickness of numerical model.
 A : area of numerical model.
 μ : viscosity of fluid.
 ΔP : applied pressure difference.

Numerical Simulations: Liquid Injection Molding Simulations (LIMS)

- Research software developed at the Center for Composite Materials University of Delaware for the simulations of mold filling stage of liquid composite molding (LCM) processes.
- **LIMS**: models flow through porous media by finite element/control volume method.

Numerical Simulations: Monte Carlo Method

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{pmatrix} K_{xx} & K_{xy} & K_{xz} \\ K_{xy} & K_{yy} & K_{yz} \\ K_{xz} & K_{yz} & K_{zz} \end{pmatrix}$$

Probability Density Function of K_{zz}

- Permeability tensors \mathbf{K} of sub-domains used to generate separate probability density functions for each component of \mathbf{K} .
- *Lognormal* probability functions used to **assign randomly permeability components** to elements of models of samples of 5 and 33 plies.
- 100 simulations performed on each model where the random permeability assignment is repeated each time.

Numerical Simulations: Effective Permeability of Sample of 5 Plies

- Average of simulations comparable with experiments on larger scale samples.
- Cv below 5% for model of area of 350 mm² (fabric RVE 25 mm²).

Effective Permeability

Coefficient of Variation

Legends: in black: simulations; colors: experiments of selected in-plane dimensions.

Numerical Simulations: Effective Permeability of Sample of 33 Plies

- Cv below 5% for model of area of 290 mm² (fabric RVE 25 mm²).

Effective Permeability

Coefficient of Variation

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Conclusions

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Journal Publications

- [Permeability of Carbon/Carbon Composites](#)

“Correlation of the permeability and porosity development of carbon/carbon composites during pyrolysis”

T. Lavaggi, F. Muhammed, L. Moretti, J.W. Gillespie, S. Advani, *Composites Part A* (2024) DOI [10.1016/j.compositesa.2024.108156](#)

“Influence of sample size on permeability of carbon-carbon composites with stochastic microstructure”

T. Lavaggi, J. W. Gillespie Jr., P. Mulye, C. Binetruy, S. Advani, *Composites Part A* (2025) DOI [10.1016/j.compositesa.2025.109126](#)

- [PoroS](#)

“A novel finite element-based method for predicting the permeability of heterogeneous and anisotropic porous microstructure”

P. Mulye, E. Syerko, C. Binetruy, A. Leygue, *Materials* (2024) DOI [10.3390/ma17122873](#)

- [LIMS](#)

“Desirable features in mold filling simulations for liquid composite molding processes”

P. Simacek, S. Advani, *Polymer Composites* (2004) DOI [10.1002/pc.20029](#)

- [Additional publications on Carbon/Carbon Composites](#)

“Relating the microstructural and glass transition temperature evolution of a carbon-carbon composite precursor during pyrolysis using thermomechanical analysis” DOI [10.1002/app.54526](#)

“Pyrolysis schedule optimization of benzoxazine-derived carbon/carbon composites through reaction rate optimization”

DOI [10.1016/j.ceramint.2023.03.121](#)

“Influence of pyrolytic decomposition on the microstructure evolution of benzoxazine-derived carbon-carbon composites” DOI [10.1007/s10853-022-08007-9](#)

“Influence of material and process parameters on microstructure evolution during the fabrication of carbon-carbon composites: a review” DOI [10.1007/s10853-021-06401-3](#)